

The discovery that global warming is accelerating.

By Michael Jenkins.

One of the UK home population.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17183234>

To encourage and inspire,
world population climate action,
all our world's climate scientists,
really need to begin fairly asking us,
our whole world population,
in all our world's news services:

**“Please can we, our whole world population,
please really care, and please really choose,
to use, less or much less, carbon combustion energy,
every day, now and forevermore, please.”**